

Semantic Graph-Driven Intelligent Recommendation of Similar Cases for Urban Regeneration

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Abstract: As cities transition from sprawling expansion to resource-constrained stock renewal, urban regeneration has become pivotal for enhancing the efficiency of urban resource utilization and unlocking latent urban potential. However, the spatial fragmentation and intricate interrelationships among current regeneration units hinder the availability of reference cases for informed decision-making. This study proposes a semantic graph-driven approach for the intelligent recommendation of similar cases in urban regeneration, grounded in the framework of ‘case representation – case extraction – case application.’ Anchored in the paradigm of geographical case-based reasoning, we develop a case representation model that captures both entities and their spatially constrained relationships, enabling a comprehensive expression of case features across relational and spatial dimensions. By integrating domain knowledge from urban planning and large language models, relevant case information is extracted from unstructured regeneration texts. This, in conjunction with multi-source geospatial data, supports the construction of a multidimensional knowledge graph for urban regeneration. A similarity computation model that incorporates temporal, spatial, and semantic attributes of cases is further designed to enable geographically grounded, quantifiable recommendations. Experimental validation based on urban regeneration documents and diverse geospatial datasets—such as land use, points of interest, and population distribution—demonstrates a joint entity-relation extraction accuracy of 0.874 and a recommendation precision of 0.81, substantiating the effectiveness of the proposed information extraction and multidimensional similarity matching method. Through systematic case modeling, efficient information extraction, and precise similarity assessment, this study significantly enhances the retrieval efficiency of urban regeneration cases, enabling intelligent recommendation of analogous cases and supporting spatial restructuring for high-quality urban development.

Keywords: Knowledge graph; Urban renewal cases; Case recommendation